

dialkyltin dialkoxides and pointed out that remarkably high intensity of the C—O bands in these compounds is due to $p_{\pi}-d_{\pi}$ bonding between the oxygen and tin atoms. The intensity of this absorption in the present investigation is usually weak to medium, which may be due to insignificant $p_{\pi}-d_{\pi}$ bonding between the oxygen and thallium atoms on account of the electron withdrawing effect of phenyl and naphthyl group in these compounds. Tl—O stretching vibration in the compounds appears at 310 ± 5 which is close to the reported value for dialkylthallium alkoxides¹¹.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Osmium with 2 : 2'-bis (2-pyridyl)-benzothiazole and 2 : 2'-bis(o-mercaptophenyl)-acetylacetonato anil

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SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC determination and stability constants of the complexes of osmium with 2 : 2'-bis(2-pyridyl)-benzothiazole (Reagent I) and

2 : 2'-bis(o-mercaptophenyl)-acetylacetonato anil (Reagent II) respectively, have been made. The maximal absorption being 490 nm and 480 nm for reagents I and II, at 0.50 to 3.0M and 0.10 to 2.0M HCl medium, whereas sensitivities are $0.0200 \mu \text{ g cm}^{-2}$ and $0.0250 \mu \text{ g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The optimal ranges for Beer's law are 4 to 16 ppm and 4 to 12 ppm for reagents I and II, the per cent. relative analysis errors being 2.60 and 2.74 respectively, whereas molar extinction coefficient values are $1.0 \times 10^4 \text{ mole cm}^{-1}$ and $7.25 \times 10^3 \text{ mole cm}^{-1}$. Composition of the complexes are evaluated and stability constants were calculated by the Leden's and Rosenstein's methods, which agree quite well.

Organic reagents having N, O or S donor atoms have been described for spectrophotometric determination of osmium^{1,2}. They offer varied nature of sensitivity and selectivity under experimental conditions. Chelating agents containing C—S bridge or S—S bridge have a tendency to give coloured complexes with osmium. Sulphur can take part in M→L back π -bonding causing therein high stability. In this present paper, spectrophotometric determination of osmium and evaluation of stability constants have been described with reagents like benzothiazole containing C—S bridge and a Schiff's base anil containing S—S bridge. Both the reagents give red or red-violet coloured complexes with osmium and are suitable for spectrophotometric determination. The systems of osmium complexes are sensitive, follow Beer's law over a considerable range. The stability constants of the complexes were evaluated by a few standard methods where they agree quite well.

Reagents, Apparatus and Solutions

Preparation of 2 : 2'-bis(2-pyridyl)-benzothiazole [Reagent-I]

2 : 2'-bis pyridyl ketone (A.R. grade) and 2-amino thiophenol (Fluka) in 1 : 1 mole ratio was refluxed in absolute alcohol for 6 hours. The reaction mixture on cooling gave pale yellow crystals. The product was recrystallised from absolute ethanol to give white needle-shaped crystals. Yield—40% m.p. 132°. On analysis : found, 69.79% C, 4.36% H, and 14.30% N, Calc. for $C_{17}H_{13}N_3S$, 70.00% C, 4.47% H and 14.43% N.

2 : 2'-bis(o-mercaptophenyl)-acetyl acetonato anil (a Schiff's base) [Reagent-II].

Acetyl acetone (BDH) 10 g and 2-amino-thiophenol (Fluka) 25 g were refluxed in benzene medium in presence of 25 ml of freshly distilled pyridine for 6 hours when a deep orange mixture was obtained. On cooling at room temperature for 2 days, orange crystals separated out which was washed with ligroin and dried in vacuum.

Yield—2.5 g ; m.p. 184°

Analysis : found, 64.27% C, 5.61% H and 8.49% N
 Calc. for $C_{17}H_{18}N_2S_2$, 64.97% C, 5.76% H and 8.91% N.

A Hilger uvivisek spectrophotometer using 1 cm glass or quartz cells was used for measurements of absorptions.

Standard osmium(VIII) solution was prepared as suggested by Ayres and Wells³ and standardized⁴ iodometrically.

Standard solution of hydrochloric acid and of diverse ions were prepared from A.R. grade reagent and determined by standard methods.

Reagent solutions

Solutions of the reagents 0.2% w/v and 0.1% w/v were prepared in 95% ethanol for reagents I and II respectively.

Coloured complexes were obtained by adding ethanolic solutions of reagents to osmium(VIII) solution. Since, osmium(VIII) is reduced to osmium(VI) with ethanol used as a solvent for reagent solution, the colour reactions are actually with osmium(VI) ions.

Absorption spectra

Absorbances of the complex with Reagent-I containing 6 ppm of osmium and 2.5 ml of 0.2% (w/v) reagent solution at 2 M HCl concentration were measured against reagent blank from 400 to 675 nm and maximal absorbance was found to be at 490 nm, whereas absorbance of the reagent in that region is very low. With Reagent-II absorbances were measured of a solution containing 5 ppm of osmium and 4 ml of 0.1% (w/v) reagent solution at 1 M HCl concentration from 420 to 600 nm. The absorbances of the reagent continuously decreased and at 470 nm and above had no absorption while maximal absorption of the complex was at 480 nm.

Effect of variables

With Reagent-I maximal colour intensity was found to be in 0.50 to 3.0 M hydrochloric acid medium. With 4 ppm of osmium 0.4 ml of 0.2% (w/v) reagent solution was found to be sufficient for complete colour development. With the same amount of osmium, up to 4.0 ml of 0.2% (w/v) reagent solution had no adverse effect on absorbance values. With Reagent-II, maximal absorption was found in 0.10 to 2.0 M HCl concentration. With 5 ppm of osmium 1 mole of 0.1% (w/v) reagent solution was found to be sufficient for complete colour development and with same amount of metal up to 5.0 ml of 0.2% (w/v) reagent solution did not effect the absorption of the complex system. The complexes are stable for 3 and 2 hours with Reagents I and II respectively. In both the cases, ethanol up to 70% concentration used as solvent in reagent

solutions had no adverse effect on the absorption systems. Spectral studies were made at room temperature $27 \pm 2^\circ$.

Recommended procedure

Reagent-I

In a 25 ml. volumetric flask, take 1.5 ml of osmium(VIII) solution containing 0.1 mg and add 2.5 ml of 0.2% (w/v) reagent solution followed by 10 ml of 5 M hydrochloric acid solution and make up the volume with double distilled water. Measure the absorbance value against a reagent blank.

Reagent-II

In a 25 ml volumetric flask, take 1.25 ml of osmium(VIII) solution having 0.1 mg/ml and add 4 ml of 0.1% (w/v) reagent solution. After 5 min. an amber colour developed. And 5 ml of 5 M hydrochloric acid solution and make up the volume and measure absorbance as usual.

Beer's law

The complex system with Reagent I obeys Beer's law from 1 to 16 ppm of osmium, the optimal⁵ range being 4 to 16 ppm. Sensitivity⁶ and % relative analysis error⁷ being $0.0200 \mu g cm^{-2}$ and 2.60, respectively. With Reagent II Beer's law is obeyed from 2 to 16 ppm of osmium, optimal range being 4 to 12 ppm. Sensitivity and % relative analysis error being $0.0250 \mu g cm^{-2}$ and 2.74 respectively. The molar extinction coefficients of the complexes with Reagents I and II, evaluated by extrapolation are found to be $1.0 \times 10^4 mole cm^{-1}$ at 490 nm and $7.25 \times 10^3 mole cm^{-1}$ at 480 nm respectively.

Composition of the complexes

Compositions of the complexes with Reagents I and II were determined by Job's method⁸ of continuous variation and were confirmed by molar ratio method⁹. In both the cases, Job's method indicated that osmium and reagent are in the ratio of 1:1 and mole ratio method confirmed this finding.

Effect of diverse ions

To find out the effect of diverse ions on the complex system, solutions containing a definite amount of osmium(VIII) but varying amounts of foreign ions were prepared and absorbances were measured. A deviation of 0.005 unit of absorbance value from the original was considered as interference. Of the tested cations and anions, with 4 ppm of osmium(VIII) following ions did not interfere in ppm unit.

Reagent-I	Reagent-II
Mn(II)-200, Cu(II)-100	Mn(II)-100, Co(II)-50
Ru(III)-200, Ir(III)-400	Ru(III)-100, Ir(III)-400
Fe(III)-50, Co(III)-100	Pt(II)-50
PO_4^{3-} -400, Citrate-100	PO_4^{3-} -400, Borate-200
HF_2^- -200, Borate-100	
Tartrate-200, SCN^- -200	
NO_3^- -200	

With Reagent-I, ions like Pt(II), Pd(II), Ni(II), V(V) and oxalate interfere.

With Reagent-II, Pd(II), Cu(II), Fe(III), V(V), Ni(II), SCN⁻, Citrate, Tartrate, HF₂⁻ however interfered the complex system.

However, to overcome interference due to cations, there are recommended procedures¹⁰ by a prior distillation of Os(VIII) in HNO₃ medium as OsO₄.

Degree of dissociation, dissociation constant and stability constant

Using the equation of Harvey and Manning¹¹, the degree of dissociation and dissociation constant were calculated and found to be 0.184 and 1.79×10^{-6} for Reagent-I and 0.159 and 1.27×10^{-6} for Reagent II respectively.

Stability constants were calculated^{12,13} from molar ratio data according to Leden's method¹⁴. Using the following equation: $\phi = 1 + \beta_1[L] + \beta_2[L]^2 + \dots + \beta_n[L]^n$, where $\phi = \frac{CM}{[M]}$ for the equation $M + nL = ML_n$. The value of the function, ψ_1 is obtained from the equation¹⁴,

$\psi_1 = \frac{\phi - 1}{[L]} = \beta_1 + \beta_2[L] + \dots$ for 1 : 1 (M : L) systems $\psi_1 = \beta_1$.

Stability constants were also evaluated by Rosenstein's method¹⁵.

For 1 : 1 metal-ligand system at an wave length where metal and reagent have no or negligible absorbance, i.e.,

$$\epsilon_0 = \epsilon_L \approx 0,$$

$M + L \rightleftharpoons ML$, stability constant β_1 is given by

$$\frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_1 - \epsilon} = \beta_1[L]$$

In both the cases notations have their usual significance. β_1 was evaluated graphically in both the cases and found as follows :

	Reagent-I	Reagent-II
Stability constant calculated by,—		
(i) Leden's method	1.3×10^6	0.90×10^6
(ii) Rosenstein's method	2.5×10^6	2.0×10^6
Mean β_1	1.9×10^6	1.45×10^6

Results and Discussion

The benzothiazole reagent could satisfactorily be used for spectrophotometric determination of osmium with limited interference and is suitable for routine laboratory analysis. The Schiff's base anil reagent though cannot tolerate a number of foreign

ions in the system, it is the first one of a series of di-anils. Other reagents which have already been utilised by the authors, where $-\text{CH}_3$ groups of the diketones have been replaced by other radicals to give more sensitive and selective reagents for determination of osmium. These reagent are not only restricted for use to osmium only but could be extended to the field of other platinum metals, such as Pt and Pd. Such studies are in progress in this laboratory. The authors have already prepared three more reagents by condensing benzoylacetone, dibenzoyl methane and thenoyl trifluoro acetone with 2-aminothiophenol and their studies on osmium and other platinum metals will be reported shortly.

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A New Method for the Geochemical Exploration of Trace Amount of Barium and Strontium Using SPADNS

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IN view of the need for a rapid method of the determination of trace amount of Ba and Sr, a direct colorimetric method has been developed using SPADNS¹⁻⁴ for the micro-determination of barium as little as 0.2 μ g and of strontium as little